

From Defuturing to (Re)Futuring: Designing in Uncertainty to Catalyze Agency, Resistance and Hope

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Abstract: This paper explores the transition from defuturing-design practices that undermine the viability of future life to (re)futuring, a design orientation grounded in futures literacy, strategic foresight, and designer agency and responsibility. Design must evolve beyond short-term, solutionist thinking to engage with complex systems, long-term consequences, and the socioecological implications of its outputs. The integration of futures literacy and strategic foresight into design practice informs a proposed meta theory of prospective design, which offers a pathway to more anticipatory, inclusive, just, and sustainable futures. The paper then examines the dual role of artificial intelligence (AI) in this context: as both a potential defuturing force when used uncritically, and as a tool for expanding imagination and supporting futures literacy when applied reflexively. Practical implications include the need for design education and practice to embed futures literacy as a core competency, enabling designers to navigate uncertainty, anticipate unintended consequences, and make ethically informed decisions.

Practical Implications: The paper calls for a shift in design culture from “move fast and break things” to “move slow and nurture things”, and highlights the importance of interdisciplinary collaboration, critical reflection, and long-term thinking in shaping equitable and resilient futures.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence in Design; Design Ethics; Defuturing; Futures Literacy; Prospective Design; Strategic Foresight.

1. Introduction: Designing in Complexity and Uncertainty

Design functions within and as part of complex systems. Complex systems are “systems where the collective behavior of their parts entails emergence of properties that can hardly, if not at all, be inferred from properties of the parts” and are recognizable by characteristics including multiple variables in ever-shifting contexts of interdependency (<https://cssociety.org/about-us/what-are-cs>). Sensing or noticing potentially important messages in complex systems can be problematic because of our interconnectedness and simultaneous immersion in multiple streams of interaction with many different parts of the environment or system, and because almost everything is interconnected with other parts in complex and unpredictable ways.

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2. Futuring and Defuturing: Temporal Dimensions of Design

The integration of ‘futuring’ – the practice of considering ‘the future’ – in design adds a temporal context and therefore additional complexity to designing in complex systems. Smith (2020) describes futuring as a practical, structured process of exploring, envisioning, and preparing for multiple possible futures. Rather than predicting a single outcome, futuring is about sensing and scanning for early signals of change to make sense of complex trends and uncertainties, and to contribute to building a culture that continuously adapts to change. Voros (2003), Slaughter (2004), and Schultz (2006) emphasize that futuring is not about forecasting with certainty, but about cultivating the capacity to navigate uncertainty, envision multiple alternative futures, and enable people and organizations to make better decisions about tomorrow in the present.

In 1999, Fry (2020) proposed the idea of ‘defuturing’, a deconstructive method to expose fundamental flaws in the designed world around us. Defuturing refers to the process and underlying economic, social, and cultural models by which human action and inaction, especially through unsustainable design, technology, and economic systems, undermine the possibility of a viable future. Fry argues that many aspects of modern life contribute to the active and passive destruction of the ecological, social, and cultural conditions necessary for sustaining life over time.

3. Prospective Design and the Rise of Futures Literacy

Emerging from similar concerns and the paucity of long-term thinking in design, ‘prospective design’ (Engeler, 2017) holds futuring at its core. Prospective design explicitly integrates anticipatory thinking and strategic foresight into design practice, acknowledging the role of design and designers in shaping multiple alternative futures, with an emphasis on agency, decision-making, and taking responsibility for its (un)intended consequences.

As noted by Roberts (2025), there has been a growing focus on environmental concerns and increased attention on speculative design, design fiction, and design futures in recent years. There is a broader interest in the potential of design to envision, anticipate, and actualize just futures while both criticising wasteful design practices and calling for more socially and ecologically responsible approaches. This reflects the emergence of ‘futures literacy’: the capacity or ability to make use of anticipation, to understand how the future is imagined and used to make decisions in the present (Miller, 2015). Futures literacy is a capability to be developed, like reading and writing, that enables individuals to better understand the role of ‘the future’ in their thoughts and actions, enabling them to anticipate change and respond or adapt more effectively (Miller, 2015).

4. From Theory to Practice: Applying Futures Thinking in Design

Opportunities to ‘use the future’ may not be deliberately or explicitly part of a design process or project, but design’s role in shaping futures is undeniable in practice. Research shows that futures and strategic foresight (FSF) methods and tools are used in some design practice by some design practitioners (Engeler, 2017; Hines & Zindato, 2016; Potter & Candy, 2019). But does that make design futures literate? Is futures literacy evident in design practice overall? Arguably not. There is some awareness of the need to think (and design) for the longer term, but what is understood or defined as ‘longer term’ is a variable determined by the context of the design or futuring activity. Karlssen states that being futures literate is not the result of arbitrary daydreaming or imagining; instead, it involves images of futures produced through rigorous and specific processes that include the structured stimulus of anticipation.

Design requires designers to invoke ‘the future’ in creating products and services that are appropriate, desired, and suitable for the needs of people and their use/experience context. The decisions designers make about ‘the future’ are an intrinsic part of the design process. While no designer can predict the future or the exact conditions, needs and desires of its systems or inhabitants, inevitably design privileges one future over others when decisions are made. As argued by Evans (2014), “Placing designers unprepared into this context of rapid change and increasing possibilities without appropriate research tools is likely to be problematic. What design is lacking is a structured method for conducting research that informs future-oriented design projects”.

5. Temporalities of Design: Timeframes, Tools, and Tensions

Not having a futures lens to use is different from not knowing there is a futures lens to use. There may be no inherent future-orientedness in design, given that timeframes of projects vary and design solutions and outcomes may be delivered in weeks or years (Mangnus et al., 2021). The temporal realm that is deemed ‘the future’ is often socially constructed and directly linked to the futuring activity at hand (Mangnus et al., 2021). FSF typically adopts the framing of the future in

short, medium, and long-term perspectives – short being 5–10 years, medium 10–20, and long-term 20 years and beyond (Nordlund, 2012). Longer term could be understood in design as 5 or 10 years away depending on the perspective of those engaged in the work and the nature of the project e.g. product or industrial design vs communication design or organisation, policy, architectural or urban design; this has been exacerbated by the global pandemic in 2020-2022 which affected every industry and sector but particular some that design directly interfaces from retail, consumer goods and transport, to workplaces, OH&S and supply chain. Nordlund (2012) notes that other than when scale terms are used in futures research and forecasting – i.e., short, medium, or long – FSF conceives of time as a loose and boundary condition. For Miller, the future is a time “later-than-now” (Miller, 2015).

FSF has a clear action orientation; therefore, a specific and relatable timeframe is usually limited to a few decades or a generation or so. Design has an outcome or solution orientation and typically operates in shorter timeframes. For a client that needs solutions in the next six weeks, three months, or slightly longer, the focus is typically whether the solution can influence future commercial goals, not whether it may have implications and impact over a much longer time scale. The same phenomenon is clear in many media headlines and general communication for ‘the future of...’ which frequently introduces predictions or narratives focused on anywhere from the next 6-12 months to ad hoc immediate responses at a future point in time that could be seconds or years away.

6. Futures Literacy in Design and Innovation

Futures literacy helps people and organisations imagine new possibilities and consider the longer-term implications of choices and actions in the present. As a core foundation of a futures-focused problem-solving equation, design shapes the conditions of existence and experience, as well as the conditions of designing and the consequences of design. Whether designing a website, a business card, a brand of soup, a business model, or government policy, futures literate designers can help stop some of the world’s ongoing challenges from worsening, anticipate how current crises could be mitigated, and maybe even prevent many new problems from emerging.

Design is essentially focused on thinking and making that can shape and alter design–material practices that become blinkers, obfuscating its influence in futures. Just as Carbon Tunnel Vision (Cognizant, 2022) prevents organizations from seeing beyond carbon emissions to the wider spectrum of important environmental and social impacts such as biodiversity loss, land conversion, resource scarcity, overconsumption or inequality, design cannot be positioned as ‘the way’ to enlighten organizations or provide ‘the solution’ to solve existential challenges let alone wicked problems. As discussed in Chapters 1 and 2, a wicked problem is inherently complex, “unique” and “ill-defined” (Rittel & Webber, 1973, p.163¹). No matter what is suggested in the litany of design, there is no definitive formula for resolving a wicked problem because “there are no ends to the causal chains that link interacting open systems” (Rittel & Webber, 1973).

As argued by Fry (2009), design is implicated in manufacturing and production processes leading to pollution, resource depletion, and waste: design has driven sociocultural- and bio-insecurity that has unsustainability as the prevailing global condition. Design’s complicity in materialism and consumption, predominant Global North conventions and paradigms, direct contribution to the paradigm of growth, and fantasy of so-called sustainable - and possibly regenerative – design, all limit its potential to shift the trajectory of the futures it is already shaping.

Tonkinwise (2015) makes the need for futures literacy explicit: “A designer who does not have a clear sense of the wider future they are trying to design by introducing a new product into the world is not only unconvincing but irresponsible.” Any idea about the future is best considered **a subjective judgement based on the present from a specific positionality**; ideas are likely to change as the external, internal, and temporal contexts for an idea change. Design gives form to these ideas, capturing uncertainty in material ways.

Futures literacy empowers the imagination and enhances people’s ability to prepare and co-invent speculative futures that can be made through design. Futures literacy also fosters design’s agency for radical change. Hoffmann (2022) calls for interdisciplinary approaches to forge creative paths toward urban resilience, combining speculative design and FSF with planning, co-design, community- and strengths-based approaches, and other methods and tools that already exist. Along with the recent contributions of Wizinsky (2022), Costanza-Chock (2020), Monteiro (2017), Tonkinwise (2014a, 2014b, 2015) and Fry (2009, 2020) there is a global cadre of voices, which has grown in size and volume over at least the last two decades, challenging design to resist capitalistic, technocratic, Global North ways of thinking and making and to seek anti-colonial, living-systems-oriented lenses instead.

Futures literacy may help design better recognize and prepare for experiences, interventions, and disruptions that we may not understand until we encounter them. Uncertainty is primarily about the future, while ambiguity is about the present (Arend, 2020; Kim, 2023). Design works from ambiguity. FSF works from uncertainty. This is a critical difference between

¹ Terminology such as complex or intractable instead of wicked would sometimes better serve communication of the nature of the problems (and the environments in which they exist) in design and FSF discourse

design and FSF. Ambiguity is characterised as offering relevant information although the overall meaning is unknown, providing multiple options or pathways forward to choose from, and therefore enabling multiple interpretations of the available information. Uncertainty is characterised by a lack of relevant information: it is neither available nor known.

7. Design's Ethical Burden: Responsibility, Consequences, and Agency

In both FSF and design, most decisions involve incomplete knowledge, and mostly it is the kind of knowledge that generates uncertainty over outcome probabilities. But choices and decisions still need to be made: the difference being that in design, you may have some but not all the answers or information to make such decisions, but in futuring, you may have none.

Hunt (2015) refers to unanticipated and unintended outcomes of design as design's "known unknowns". Unfortunately, many known unknowns are now evident in the world around us, material documentation of just how many design solutions and innovations have been proven to be damaging for people and the planet, directly or indirectly. Hunt also points to a range of design artefacts from cars and architecture to 3D printed guns and assembly instructions as examples of design's influence being curtailed by other actors such as marketing, accounting, and management.

Design does not happen in a vacuum. Even though design has created the conditions and implements for human and environmental tragedies, design cannot be held solely responsible for such outcomes because it is embedded in larger sociotechnical systems comprising actors from diverse domains whether engineering, law, management and strategy, manufacturing, logistics, politics, finance, sales, real estate, FMCG, retail, hospitality, tourism, marketing and advertising, technology, transport, and people as users and consumers. Planned Obsolescence – the process of becoming obsolete, unfashionable or no longer usable as part of deliberately planned business, marketing and manufacturing strategy (Kramer, 2012) - is an example of how design artifacts have typically been considered or developed not in isolation but without deep consideration of (or disregard for) the worlds in which they exist and the systems that surround and interact with them. Monteiro (2017) argues for designers to use their agency, whether from within large-scale corporate environments to small design shops. Monteiro (2017) is clear that designers "need to fear the consequences of our work more than we love the cleverness of our ideas," but acknowledges that an ethical backbone has its consequences, including the fear of the economic implications of ethical choices is real. There is arguably an ethical responsibility to generations and futures yet to come that adds to design's already increasing load, but individual designers can make changes and/or choices that reflect a prospective design approach.

FSF offers robust ways for futuring: studying futures and considering future-oriented design projects at deeper levels that support transformative speculative design and design fiction. FSF methods and tools provide the relevant tools to help designers think through the 'known unknowns', the unintended consequences of design, and to consider the implications of what is being designed and why. Navigating different kinds of possible futures requires new thinking, imagining, and acting, yet design is neither truly equipped for nor adequately prepared for that challenge. Wizinsky (2022), Pawlyn and Ichioka (2022) and Monteiro (2017) focus on necessary shifts in design from academic and industry perspectives, while Chen and Hsu (2020), Scupelli et al. (2019) focus on embedding futures literacy and implementing FSF tools and methods in education, not just design education.

8. Problematizing Design

If design is the answer, why are there still so many problems? (and questions?)

Design is increasingly tasked with solving problems that are complex, ambiguous, and subjective, which usually need to be (re)structured before they can be solved (or otherwise dealt with) (Dorst, 2004). For poorly structured or misunderstood problems, the restructuring may be far more challenging than designing a solution.

Most problems are 'messy', whether ill-defined, complex and subtle, vague and poorly expressed or understood, with an underlying systemic nature and as many subjective versions as there are people involved. These kinds of problems – typically wicked (Rittel & Webber, 1973) – They are rarely easy to define and even harder to resolve with a simple solution or a 3-day sprint. The contemporary context for design, focusing on complexity, rapid change, and innovation as much as competitive advantage, empathy, and walls covered with sticky notes, frames the broad understanding of how the tools of design are utilised.

Design may have "moved from the kids' table up to the adults', wielding new levels of power and impact in contexts as diverse as business, government policy, healthcare, and international development," but it is yet to be considered "futures fit" (Koskelo & Nousiainen, 2019). Papanek and Fuller (1972) highlighted this dilemma in professional design practice over 50 years ago; today, design expects to be treated as an adult even when it does not take the repercussions of its actions seriously.

Time (both the time it takes to define a problem and reach a solution, and the lifetime of a solution) and impact (the viability, feasibility and desirability of a solution as well as its consequences) may bring about an increase in the scrutiny of design. If design is to become ‘futures fit’ it must move beyond simplistic responses to existential crises by considering not just the solution or a desired future state but also the undesirable futures and the consequences of design’s influence in the present.

9. Can Design ‘Use the Future’? Embedding FSF in Practice

Design in a linear economic model has provided products and services at every scale. But all those design decisions are based on present needs, systems, supply chains, business models, and available resources rather than what might be available and necessary over the longer term. Designing for yesterday means ignoring current and future environmental impact and continuing BAU; it means relying on current data that limits imagination and stymies transformation. Embedding futures literacy in design creates ways for ‘prospective design’ (Engeler, 2017) as design that holds futures at its core. By extension, designing without FSF or considering the consequences of design is effectively defuturing.

Just as design does not exist in a vacuum, the ‘future’ does not happen in a vacuum either. Inbound and outbound changes are constantly tweaking the possibilities and projections we can anticipate. Thinking about futures requires more than giving form to the images of futures, especially the used futures and flat-pack futures and because ‘thinking about the future’ is fundamentally part of the design process, the issue may not be the thinking about but how and why the thinking is done.

What is missing is an explicit means to ‘use the future’ in design praxis: engaging with futures, using methodologies (and epistemologies) that open up or narrow down a particular range of what is possible and imaginable, is critical to building futures literacy. Using the future brings about changes in the present that transform the next temporal context i.e. they create the preferred or alternative futures imagined.

While design is not necessarily required to think about ‘the future’ in its broadest sense, the more perfunctory but populist version of design as problem-solving, which evades any sincere consideration of the deeper (root) causes of problems, prevails. The 2020-23 global pandemic, IPCC report (2022) referring to climate collapse and the mainstreaming of polycrisis at Davos in 2023 are worldwide almost mainstream warnings of the need for radical change, including design changes to render it capable of considering its economic, social, and environmental impact by putting future generations at its core.

The risk, therefore, is twofold: 1) that (insufficient) time is given to thinking about futures or the consequences of design in the design process; and 2) that designers have (insufficient) FSF knowledge and skills, leading to a lack of futures literacy in process and practitioners. The rush to solution, driven by pressing needs such as deadlines, budgets, sales figures, people’s health, or day-to-day lives, or by short-termism², or simply by the legacy of poor risk and economic growth forecasts that turned out to be wrong, prevents design for the long term in creating products, services, systems, or organizations, or acting on the omnipresent threats of an ecological crisis. The influence of short-termism looms large, threatening to drive our current and proximate civilizations to breakdown, rather than leveraging design agency to create a culture that values longer time horizons and responsibility for shared futures (Costanza-Chock 2020; Krznaric, 2020).

10. The Risk of Defuturing by Design

Design: it influences and creates every aspect of life and lived experience. Design, therefore, must acknowledge its responsibility and culpability as a major contributor to the idea and construction of a society almost entirely based on the production of goods and services for consumption. Design must also recognize its role in the ‘move fast and break things’ era that still pushes for disruption and innovation despite the societal, geopolitical, and environmental ramifications (Satell, 2019): it is directly implicated in global system collapse (Henriksen & Mishra, 2020; Silliman et al., 2013).

From creating habitable environments on Earth and colonies on Mars to hydrogen-fuelled transport, SolarPunk, climate-resilient floating city-states and interstellar travel, speculative design and speculative futures have arguably contributed to the imagining and visualisation of fascinating, uplifting, frequently technocentric and often protopian (The Technium), possible, plausible and preferred futures. However, as much as these visions might entice and excite, and perhaps even inspire, it is too easy to forget that the lenses used to imagine them focus on small slices of the world *as it is known by the protagonist* and frequently rely on technology to ‘solve’ issues that might be geopolitical, cultural or sociological, not resolvable through tech fixes or material practices, or simply beyond their purview.

Rarely is design encouraged to think about who might be left out in creating these visions: who cannot board a ship to Mars – and why? Who does not have the skills or access to the tools or resources to build a ‘seasteading’ community (<http://dismagazine.com/dystopia/evolved-lifestyles/67148/what-is-seasteading/>)? Whose labour will be used to create these new realities? Who is mining the minerals required for a SolarPunk world – and which nation’s resources and people are being traded, commoditised, and depleted in the process? Which communities may no longer exist when those so-called preferred futures become someone else’s lived reality? Whose home will have disappeared long before floating cities are built? Or, more prosaically in the present state of innovation and problem-solving, do we need to expend resources (and imagination) on a portable barista (Kickstarter), lab-produced coffee (PhysOrg) or silicon shoes for suitcase wheels (Kickstarter)?

Design can, however, embrace the kind of deliberation required for nuanced and ethical business decisions and shift towards a “Move Slow and Nurture Things” approach (Henriksen & Mishra, 2020). The slow design movement provides an evaluative tool that encourages design practice oriented to social, cultural, and environmental sustainability (Strauss & Fuad-Luke, 2008). Along with sustainable design, circular design, and regenerative design, the principles and values of slow design support behavioural change in design to deliver sustainability. Sinni (2020) proposes a shift in emphasis to “implications, rather than applications” and a push for design to ask better questions rather than focusing on (quick) answers.

11. AI and Design Futures: Opportunities and Tensions

New tools bring new challenges. Artificial Intelligence (AI) continues to provoke critical discourse around its role in creativity, imagination, and learning. Rather than viewing AI solely as a utilitarian tool or a threat to human ingenuity, it is increasingly being positioned as a partner in the creative process. AI can support human endeavour by augmenting imagination and enabling access to new ideas, particularly for individuals who may not have previously conceived of certain futures. Even when AI-generated outputs draw from “used futures,” they can still serve as novel stimuli for those encountering them for the first time, thereby expanding the imaginative horizon (Miller & Sandford, 2019).

This perspective aligns with concerns about AI’s potential to contribute to defuturing - not through overt harm, but through a paucity of imagination and over-reliance on algorithmic outputs. Fry (2009) warns that design practice can lead to defuturing when they fail to critically engage with long-term consequences. However, if AI is used to build a ‘mind catalogue’ of futures - an archive of speculative possibilities, so to speak - it may serve as a scaffold for expanding human creativity, even when it is limited to building (regurgitating) existing ideas.

There are ongoing and constant challenges to AI’s educational value. While initial critiques suggested that AI tools were limited in their ability to support creativity, newer research indicates that AI can enhance learning engagement and foster deeper cognitive involvement. Arpacı et al. (2025) found that generative AI positively influences educational sustainability by promoting personalized learning and student engagement. Zhu et al. (2025) demonstrated that AI literacy enhances creativity and academic achievement through increased self-efficacy.

These findings suggest that AI’s utility extends beyond automation; it can play a meaningful role in cultivating creative competencies and supporting learner agency. However, this potential must be balanced with awareness of AI’s environmental footprint. The energy demands of training and deploying large-scale AI models raise ethical concerns about sustainability, which must be addressed in any comprehensive evaluation of AI’s role in design and education (Vinuesa et al., 2020).

Ultimately, embedding futures literacy within design practice empowers designers to envision and create more sustainable, inclusive, and innovative futures. It fosters a culture of responsibility and foresight, ensuring that design remains a powerful tool for positive change in an ever-evolving world. On the other hand, the use of AI in design also presents challenges. There is a risk that over-reliance on AI could lead to a reduction in human creativity and critical thinking, as designers may become too dependent on algorithmic outputs. Furthermore, ethical considerations around AI, such as biases in algorithms and data privacy concerns, must be carefully managed to ensure that AI-driven design processes are inclusive and equitable (Schmelzer, 2025).

Artificial Intelligence (AI) may play a dual role in this integration. On the one hand, AI can significantly enhance futures literacy by providing designers with advanced tools for data analysis, pattern recognition, and scenario planning. AI-driven insights can help designers explore a wider range of possibilities, identify emerging trends, and develop more innovative and user-centred solutions. Additionally, AI can facilitate the creation of speculative and anticipatory designs that are informed by robust data and predictive models (Biagini, 2025).

The challenges posed by complex systems and the unpredictable nature of future contexts require designers to move beyond short-term solutions and embrace a more holistic, forward-thinking approach. This involves not only considering the immediate needs of users but also the broader societal, environmental, and ethical implications of design decisions.

12. Old Biases for New Technologies: Reflexivity in AI-Driven Design

Resistance to technology is not a new phenomenon design (Poon, 2015). It is both appropriate and necessary to acknowledge the presence of bias, whether in favour of or against artificial intelligence (AI) when considering its role, purpose and potential in design futures. But bias is not merely a flaw to be corrected; it is a condition of human judgment. In design, which is fundamentally a process of human decision-making, bias shapes what is included, what is excluded, and how priorities are established. As Buchanan (1992) and others have argued, design is not simply about creating artifacts but about making choices that reflect values and intentions.

The integration of AI into design processes foregrounds this decision-making dynamic. AI is increasingly used to automate tasks, generate content, and optimise workflows. These applications are often justified on the grounds of efficiency and scalability, enabling designers to redirect their efforts toward more strategic or creative concerns (Verganti et al., 2020). In this sense, AI can be seen as a tool that enhances human capacity by reallocating cognitive and temporal resources.

However, the deliberate use of AI in design is not value-neutral. The systems we build and the ways we use them are shaped by the assumptions embedded in their design and training data. As Newman-Griffis et al. (2022) have shown, bias in AI-assisted decision-making often arises from seemingly innocuous design choices that, in aggregate, produce significant inequities. This underscores the need for reflexivity in both the development and application of AI tools.

Fry's defuturing (2009) is particularly relevant here again. AI, depending on how it is implemented, can either support or undermine these futures. For example, generative design tools used in architecture and urban planning can optimize for environmental performance, potentially contributing to sustainability goals (Springer, 2023). Conversely, when such tools are trained on narrow datasets or prioritize efficiency over diversity, they risk reinforcing dominant aesthetics and marginalizing alternative design languages.

Moreover, the increasing reliance on AI for creative problem-solving shifts the role of the human designer. As Verganti et al. (2020) argue, while AI can automate aspects of ideation and iteration, it cannot replace the human capacity for sense-making—the ability to frame problems, interpret context, and navigate ambiguity. This repositioning of the designer as a sense-maker rather than a problem-solver has profound implications for design education and practice.

13. Conclusion: Toward a Futures-Literate Design Ethos

The integration of futures literacy into design practice is not merely an academic exercise but a necessary evolution for the field. As design continues to influence every aspect of life and lived experience, it must acknowledge its responsibility in shaping sustainable and equitable futures. By becoming futures literate, designers can better anticipate the long-term impacts of their work, navigate the complexities of uncertain futures, make futures-informed decisions, and contribute to the creation of resilient and adaptive systems.

In sum, the use of AI in design is not merely a technical decision but an ethical and strategic one. It requires careful consideration of not only what AI can do, but what it should do, and how its use aligns with broader goals of equity, sustainability, and human agency.

Author's Note on Uses of AI Tools

Microsoft Co-Pilot was used to verify and format the reference list, and to generate a draft abstract and keywords.

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